

Measuring Firm Characteristics with Natural Language

Processing (NLP) Models

An error-mitigating framework with tutorial guidance

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Daniel L. Oberski ^{1,*}
Josep Domenech ²
Javier García-Bernardo ¹
Peter Gerbrands ¹
Wolter Hassink ^{1,3}
Hadi Mohammadi ¹
Paolo Mustica ⁴
Rutger Schilpzand ^{1,5}
Arjen van Witteloostuijn ^{5,6}

¹ Utrecht University, The Netherlands

² Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain

³ IZA - Institute of Labor Economics, Bonn, Germany

⁴ University of Messina, Italy

⁵ Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, The Netherlands

⁶ Antwerp Management School, Belgium

* Corresponding author, d.l.oberski@uu.nl. Address: Padualaan 14, 3584 CH Utrecht. Tel.: +31302534700.

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Abstract

This paper develops an error-mitigating framework, including tutorial guidance, with respect to using natural language processing (NLP) and language models to measure firm characteristics from web-scraped data, such as company websites. Over the past decade, the digital presence of firms has expanded, offering researchers new opportunities to capture organizational attributes that were previously difficult to measure at a large scale. With our framework, we seek to offer three key contributions. First, we develop a taxonomy of challenges—categorized into representation errors, measurement errors, and computational errors—associated with applying NLP to firm-level web data. Second, we formulate recommendations for preventing, managing, and reporting these challenges. Drawing from the total error framework, we address potential biases, validity issues, and computational difficulties throughout the process, from data collection to data analysis. Third, using the Dutch FIRMBACKBONE initiative as an example, we illustrate the practical applications and obstacles in building reliable digital infrastructures for firm data research. The paper concludes by highlighting the importance of investment in data infrastructures to create secure, and pseudonymized datasets for academic research.

Keywords: web scraping, natural language processing (NLP), language models, text mining, online measurement

1. Introduction

Theories of firm behavior, dynamics, and performance describe the distribution and evolution of specific organizational characteristics, and their impact on the fate of organizations and their populations. Organizational researchers therefore need to measure these characteristics, which can cover a wide variety of variables: from corporate social responsibility to company age and firm valuation, and from leadership styles and labor policies to competitive strategies and position in the supply chain. A glance in the top journals publishing organizational research across different disciplines, from the *Administrative Science Quarterly* and *Academy of Management Journal* to the *American Journal of Sociology* and *Journal of Applied Psychology*, immediately reveals the vast array of characteristics being measured and studied, one quarter after the other. For a very small number of characteristics, a large number of firms can be covered, largely by benefiting from the mandatory financial and compliance data of publicly traded companies. The remaining majority of characteristics are typically measured using survey questions asked of a small number of company representatives, or through time-consuming archival work. In short, organizational measurement has been limited either in content or in coverage, or in both.

However, across the globe, organizations' increased digital presence on the open Internet has opened up another option for data collection—using natural language processing (NLP) and language models to analyze text data for scientific research after web scraping. Over the past 14 years, the number of businesses with a web presence has risen from 67 percent to 78 percent (OECD average), with some countries reaching 98 percent, as visualized in Figure 1. And websites are only one digital source of organizational data, other prominent examples being

annual reports and social media messages. Text analysis of websites, annual reports, and social media messages thus promises to capture hard-to-measure firm characteristics for much larger samples, while hugely expanding their potential coverage (Ranta et al., 2023). In addition, website data may be useful for analyses that require real-time information flows, such as monitoring the consequences of a pandemic (Dörr et al., 2022).

[Insert Figure 1 about here]

Indeed, a growing number of studies has demonstrated the potential of constructing organizational measures based on web scraping and natural language processing. In early studies, researchers used content analysis of company websites to obtain useful measures – for example, of corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosures (Gamerschlag et al., 2011) – suggesting that such measurements could be scaled up using computer-aided text analysis (CATA). CATA was subsequently applied in the following generation of research – for instance, to measure organizational culture by applying literature-derived dictionaries to letters to shareholders (Pandey & Pandey, 2019) and to measure leadership style in press releases (Marshall et al., 2023). More recently, studies have shown that natural language processing (NLP) applied to websites can effectively measure firm innovativeness (Bottai et al., 2024; Daas & van der Doef, 2021), business export orientation (Blazquez & Domenech, 2014, 2018), and being an online platform (Daas et al., 2024), among other topics. Clearly, this AI toolkit has found its way into the organizational literature, across disciplines.

Prior work in the field of organizational research introduced the idea of applying NLP in this field, and provided recommendations. Kobayashi et al. (2018a, 2018b) discuss classical text-mining techniques in organizational research, and offer a tutorial. Schmiedel et al. (2019) propose the use of topic modeling in this field, applying this analytical technique to employee

reviews of companies on an online platform, and give advice on its application. Banks et al. (2018) likewise focus on topic modeling and give best practice recommendations. Ashton et al. (2020) propose using human judges to assess the outcome of text-mining studies. Hickman et al. (2022) give an overview of practices and recommendations for text preprocessing. And Valtonen et al. (2024) recommend reporting and validation for preprocessing and topic modeling. This is just a snapshot of what has been and still is being published throughout the organizational research literature. Of course, all this is not without bottlenecks (cf. Kobayashi et al., 2018a, b). For instance, how reliable and valid are web-based text-analyzed measures (McKenny et al., 2018; Short et al., 2010; Ugur et al., 2024)? What practical difficulties arise when trying to use websites for research? And how representative is data from online sources?

Despite the existence of preliminary applications, as well as the literature on text mining and topic modeling in organizational research, to the best of our knowledge no comprehensive examination of the challenges associated with applying NLP to company website data exists. In this paper, we address this gap. First, following the literature on total error frameworks (Groves & Lyberg, 2010; Sen et al., 2021), we divide the challenges into three types: “representation errors”, “measurement errors”, and “computational errors”. After introducing our organizing framework of three types of error, we next provide an overview of existing efforts to measure organizational characteristics using language models. Our main contributions are: (1) an extensive overview of the challenges encountered associated with three types of error, and (2) a set of recommendations for preventing, dealing with, and reporting on these challenges. As a guiding example, we (3) discuss an ongoing initiative known as FIRMBACKBONE – part of the Dutch national infrastructure for the social sciences – to illustrate the key issues.

Our paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we briefly introduce the three types of error, and we give an overview of existing studies that use scraped web data to measure organizational characteristics with NLP techniques. Section 3 takes these typical steps and the total error framework as a point of departure to discuss the various errors that may arise when performing such studies, classified along the three error types. Next, Section 4 offers a brief review of available NLP algorithms. After that, Section 5 then discusses an example application in which we follow the steps in turn. ~~Before concluding, in Section 7, we reflect on the role of what is known as Explainable NLP in ensuring content validity of organizational measures.~~ Finally, Section 6 concludes and discusses a few points of development for the future.

2. Web scraping and natural language processing in organizational research

Web information has been used quite extensively already for text analysis and the development of indicators for several economic and statistical applications. The most popular use of web information has probably been for the prediction of innovation activities by individual firms. Innovativeness has been investigated by using website information from Germany (Axenbeck & Breithaupt, 2021; Kinne & Axenbeck, 2020; Kinne & Lenz, 2021), the UK (Gök et al., 2015), the EU (Ashouri et al., 2022), Germany, Austria, and Switzerland (Dahlke et al., 2024), Canada (Héroux-Vaillancourt et al., 2020), Italy (Crosato et al., 2021), and the Netherlands (Daas & van der Doef, 2021). Examples of further important applications are product development (Arora et al., 2013), geographical ties of firms (Abbasiharofteh et al., 2023; Thonipara et al., 2023), firm growth (Li et al., 2018), default of firms (Crosato et al., 2021), classification of firms (Daas et al., 2024; Occhini et al., 2023), COVID-19 (Dörr et al., 2022), the value of the firm (Crosato et

al., 2023; Jiang et al., 2023), export orientation (Blázquez & Domenech, 2018), e-commerce (Blázquez Sorian et al., 2016), and sustainability (Blázquez et al., 2018).

Several studies have also investigated quality issues related to the use of websites for organizational research. For example, Thonipara et al. (2023) demonstrate that firms in urban areas are almost twice as likely to run websites compared with those located in rural areas (see also Jiang et al., 2023). Depending on the purpose of the study, this may raise concerns regarding representativeness of firm data derived from websites. Further, several studies have investigated general features of the websites themselves, including the number of words, number of subpages and hyperlinks, text volume, and language used (e.g., Kinne & Axenbeck, 2020; Axenbeck & Breithaupt, 2021, Dahlke et al., 2024). For instance, Kinne and Axenbeck (2020) demonstrate that the size of the website is related to the size of the firm, although outliers in size of the website can be very dominant. Hence, a measure that relates to the overall volume of terms may be biased towards larger firms. More generally, several studies have tried to investigate the validity and reliability of measures directly by comparing website-derived outcomes to traditional survey measures (Gök et al., 2015; Héroux-Vaillancourt et al., 2020; Dörr et al., 2022; Dijs et al., 2024). For example, Gök et al. (2015) show that organizations' websites report more R&D activities than the organization's executives report in a survey. Alongside these established applications, recent advances in large language models (LLMs) and domain-adapted NLP pipelines have opened new possibilities for measuring complex organizational attributes at scale (Araci, 2019; Chalkidis et al., 2020; Ushio & Camacho-Collados, 2021). These techniques can handle industry-specific terms, multilingual texts, and subtle context cues more effectively than earlier methods, thus enhancing firm-level analyses (Mohammadi et al. 2025).

In the current paper, we provide a systematic classification of these and other quality issues, based on the “total error framework” familiar from the survey methodology literature (Biemer, 2010; Groves & Lyberg, 2010). Recently, this framework has been adapted to “Big Data” (Amaya et al., 2020) and digital trace data (Boeschoten et al., 2022; Sen et al., 2021). The idea behind these frameworks is simple and effective: The process of generating the data is summarized in a series of steps. At each of these steps, an error may occur, and the accumulation of all these errors is then the “total error”. This is visualized in Figure 2.

[Insert Figure 2 about here]

Figure 2 gives a highly simplified overview of the steps towards measurement of organizational constructs using natural language processing of web data. At each step, examples of errors that occur at that step are given. In practice, total error is usually not quantified; but for people involved in the collection or analysis of data, it is still useful to consider what problems may occur, what their relative severity is, how they may be prevented, and how their detrimental impact on the analysis may be ameliorated. We therefore follow the idea of a “total error” framework here, applying it to the collection of data on organizational constructs through web scraping and natural language processing. Since our primary aim is not to introduce a new total error framework here, we will follow this framework only as a guide to create a systematic inventory of potential errors and the associated mitigating strategies. For more formal frameworks, we refer to Amaya et al. (2020) and Sen et al. (2021).

First, although organizations’ online presence is large and growing, there are clear dangers of *representation errors* (see the first column in Figure 2). For example, the OECD reports 98% coverage for Finland, but only 30% coverage for Indonesia. And coverage varies

much more widely for small businesses than for medium-sized and large businesses (see Figure 1), and may do so across different industries, markets, or populations. For instance, tech companies and online stores will differ from, say, a local butchers' shop and fruit retailer in their tendency to maintain a comprehensive up-to-date web presence, or to invest in web presence to start with. When websites are the only source of data, such differences are a threat to the validity of studies that aim to comprehensively compare countries, industries, populations or other organization-related attributes correlated with web presence.

Second, measures obtained from NLP modeling may exhibit random and systematic *measurement errors* (Birkenmaier et al., 2023; Fang et al., 2022; McKenny et al., 2018; Short et al., 2010). Websites can present their own, unique kind of method bias, illustrated in the second column of Figure 2. For example, companies may perceive incentives to misrepresent their CSR policies (Gamerschlag et al., 2011), and they clearly are incentivized to lace yearly financial reports with terms appreciated by financial institutions' NLP-based sentiment classifiers (Du et al., 2024; Leippold, 2023). Such systematic biases will present a threat to the validity of studies that rely on correlating multiple measures derived in this manner (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

Furthermore, the reliability for certain concepts may be weak, while other concepts will likely be beyond the reach of website-based analyses entirely. Topics such as executive compensation and employee satisfaction plausibly belong to this latter category. Such reliability and validity issues will distort estimates of relationships when ignored (Fuller, 1987), while they can drastically reduce the effective sample size when accounted for in statistical analysis – potentially even to the point at which a small-scale survey would have been the more efficient option after all (Meng, 2018).

Third and finally, there are clear *computational errors* associated with language modeling of websites, yearly reports, or any other digital information source. Web scraping is a complex and resource-intensive undertaking that is purposefully hindered by certain entities, including all large social media platforms (Mitchell, 2018). As a result, it may not be possible, or would violate terms of service, to extract information for certain types of organizations, such as local businesses who exclusively use social media. This error type may also result from problems with data storage, linkage, and governance. Moreover, the reproducibility of both web scraping and NLP approaches generally is extremely low (Fokkens et al., 2013; Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018), a problem that makes it difficult to develop standardized measurements useful across scientific disciplines. This phenomenon also makes it possible that some published analyses using web-derived measurements will not in fact have the advertised properties when other researchers seek to leverage the same approach.

3. Seven not-so-easy steps towards representative, valid, reliable, and computationally sound measurement

3.1 From frame to sample

The first step that must be taken is to construct a list of firms from a population (top of Figure 2). In some instances, this step may be trivial – for example, when official administrative registers suffice. In other cases, the population may be difficult to define, may exceed the national boundaries of official registers, or may simply be nonexistent. An example of the latter might occur when targeting the websites of illegal businesses on the dark web (Al Nabki et al., 2017). The representation error associated with this step will be identical to that incurred for the same

step in a more traditional survey approach (or archival research, for that matter, like in the organizational ecology tradition). For further elaboration on the challenges and mitigations associated with such issues, we refer to standard works on conducting traditional business surveys (Snijkers et al., 2013).

3.2 From business sample to website URLs

The second step is to construct a list of websites from the sample of companies. While seemingly straightforward, this task is in fact fraught with complexities and challenges, because the accurate identification of a company's online presence is needed. We discuss the main challenges below.

Incomplete directories. The initial step involves determining the homepage URL of each company in the sample. Directories like Orbis¹ are commonly used for this purpose, but they have their limitations, notably the absence of website information for numerous companies. This gap necessitates alternative methods, such as using search engines to locate missing websites. That approach, however, introduces new challenges to correctly mapping corporate websites to specific companies. Moreover, the scalability is limited and costly (Kühnemann et al., 2022). Incomplete directories will lead to a sample bias akin to nonresponse in classical establishment surveys.

Expired URLs. Expired URLs represent a significant challenge. Companies often change their web addresses due to rebranding, mergers, or other business decisions. These

¹ <https://www.moody.com/web/en/us/capabilities/company-reference-data/orbis.html>.

changes are however very seldom reflected in directories, since the information is only required when the company is incorporated. In some cases, when companies keep their former domains, stale URLs are redirected to the new ones through HTTP redirections, which simplifies tracking these changes. However, this is not always the case. There exist situations where the old domain expires without redirection, breaking the link between the old and the new web addresses. To address this, regular updates and checks on company URLs are necessary. Furthermore, tools can be employed to automatically track and update URL changes, though this may not capture all domain expirations or changes. Again, this challenge will lead to a type of “nonresponse”.

Inaccurate URLs. The issue of inaccurate URLs is another major hurdle. These are URLs that are valid, but do not correspond to the intended company. This inaccuracy can arise from errors in directories or expired domains bought by a different company. To mitigate this, a thorough verification process is required. This process often involves cross-referencing the website content with known company information, such as physical addresses, VAT numbers, or other identifiers. However, this method has its limitations as not all companies display such information on their websites, or they do but inaccurately. Ensuring the accuracy of URLs is a labor-intensive process, and may result in a significant reduction of the usable data set if strict verification standards are applied. This type of error may lead to “nonresponse” bias, but it can also result in “entity confusion”: linkage errors between a company and its website, leading to measurement errors. Methods for checking the accuracy of URLs are described in Barcaroli et al. (2016) and Bottai et al. (2023).

Companies without websites. There are instances where companies do not have a dedicated website. This could be due to a lack of online activity, which varies by country and sector, as well as firm characteristics (such as size). Alternatively, some companies rely on third-

party platforms for their online presence. For example, small businesses selling on Amazon may not see the need for an individual website, relying instead on Amazon for their online presence. It is also common for micro companies to lack their own websites, opting instead to set up a simple page on platforms like Facebook, Instagram, or other social media sites. Depending on the study design, this error may only lead to item missingness, but it may also result in complete “nonresponse”.

HTTPS versus HTTP. Nowadays, most corporate websites are accessible using the Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS). HTTPS provides secure, encrypted communication for websites, whereas the legacy Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) does not offer this level of security. However, not all websites have updated to the new standard, and the information in *https://www.website.com* and *http://www.website.com* may differ, leading to outdated information and measurement error. Often, old websites from smaller companies use only HTTP. A common approach is to request the HTTPS version, and if that fails, to request the HTTP version of the same website.

3.3 From URLs to scraped data

Once the set of target URLs has been established, they must be accessed by a web crawler. A web crawler, also known as a web robot or spider, is a software program designed for systematically browsing the World Wide Web to download web pages (Najork & Heydon, 2002). The process begins with a predefined set of “seed” URLs. The crawler then selects one URL from this set, retrieves the corresponding web page, extracts all URLs contained within that page linking to the same company, and incorporates any previously unknown URLs back into the set. This process continues iterating, as the crawler does traverse vast portions of the web. Companies’ homepage URLs are used as seeds for the crawler. After that, the main challenge

lies in defining which linked contents constitute the company website for data retrieval purposes, which includes deciding on the scope of domains and subdomains, types of objects to access, and the depth of crawling.

Company-website relationships. A key challenge when analyzing corporate websites is to establish the level of analysis. This issue may lead to entity definition error. The general public's understanding of a "company" (e.g., Apple) sharply contrasts with the legal understanding of a company, in which all the corporate entities associated with a company are separate entities linked by ownership relations. Some of these separate corporate entities may have their own website (for instance, country-specific or brand-specific websites). And one website can also serve several corporate entities, as is often the case with franchises and distributors. Most commonly, the level of analysis is the ultimate owner of the company (e.g., APPLE INC.), and the information from separate corporate entities (e.g., Apple UK Ltd., Apple Holding UK Ltd., and Apple Retail UK Ltd.) needs to be aggregated.

Website scope. Companies often have multiple domains or subdomains, including a generic .com domain as well as national domains such as .it, .co.jp, .nl, *et cetera*. Although they are different from a technical point of view, and although they are often linked to separate corporate entities, the websites often have overlapping information. A comprehensive approach, considering all similar domains (for instance, domains with the same second-level but different top-level domain), ensures a more complete data collection.

Language. Companies, especially large(r) ones that operate internationally, provide their corporate websites in several languages (often the local language as well as English, as a minimum). A comprehensive approach, collecting all languages, is often preferred. However, as

we detail below, analyzing websites in different languages will create new challenges during the analysis.

Types of objects to access. Websites consist of various types of objects, including HTML pages, images, PDFs, and more. Deciding which objects to access depends on the nature of the information sought. While HTML pages are generally used as main sources of textual information, PDFs and images may also contain valuable data. The challenge lies in determining which types of objects will yield the most relevant information without unnecessarily expanding the scope of data collection. An additional challenge is that content types are not known until the object was downloaded. Sometimes, it can be guessed from the URL (like .pdf), but this is not always reliable. Recent frameworks for extracting text from PDFs and images using neural approaches or layout-aware models (Wang et al. 2023) have made this step more robust, but also more computationally demanding. The actual content type is known only after accessing the data, which increases the computational complexity of the crawling process, and can introduce computational errors.

Crawling depth. Determining the crawling depth is a significant consideration. This refers to how many layers deep from the homepage the crawler goes into a website. Depth 0 refers to the home page, while depth 1 is the first set of linked pages, depth 2 consists of the pages linked from the linked pages, *et cetera*. Setting a threshold is key to reduce the computational demands of the crawling process – some websites have millions of separate pages. It is also key to avoid loops during the crawling process, in which the crawler gets stuck in a cycle of repetitive content. This can be done by keeping track of the pages that have already been crawled to avoid following them again. Additionally, websites often generate slightly different

responses for the same content request, leading to duplicates. Identifying and eliminating such duplications is essential for maintaining the quality of the dataset.

Avoiding duplicates. The same URL can be written in many ways and may be disambiguated by the browser or server. For example, `http://www.website.com`, `https://www.website.com`, `http://website.com`, and `https://website.com` will, in most instances, point to the same information. Similarly, URLs can have queries and fragments (e.g., `https://website.com/path?query=value#fragment`). Fragments are often used to navigate to a specific part of a page, such as a particular piece of content, and they need to be removed to avoid duplicates. Queries are used to provide additional information to the server. Given the wide range of queries available, especially in websites to filter specific sets of products, the researcher may also want to remove the query from the URL.

Technical challenges. Several technical challenges arise in web crawling. Expired domains or temporarily unavailable servers can disrupt access. Browser technologies, such as JavaScript redirections, pose difficulties for simpler crawling scripts. While the decline of Flash content has eased scraping challenges, new issues such as content loops and duplication still exist. Anyway, these challenges are not exclusive for web-based monitoring of companies, as this is also a well-known issue for search engines (Massimino, 2016).

Ethical considerations and network etiquette. The researcher should respect network etiquette. This involves avoiding server overload and maintaining a crawl rate that does not trigger the website's defense mechanisms against potential denial-of-service attacks. Ethical crawling respects the server's capacity, ensuring that the data collection process does not disrupt the normal operation of the website (Eurostat, 2020). Researchers should also respect the

robots.txt file contained in the base URL. This file is used to give instructions to web crawlers about which pages should not be processed.

3.4 From scraped objects to content

After the media objects have been scraped from the URL, they must be further processed into content. This content may be pure text, but can also include metadata, images, video, PDFs, and other content. Each of these types of content may provide a different view on certain variables of interest to organizational research. For instance, code analysis may provide insight into a company's digital sophistication. And each type of data requires different algorithmic processing tools. In this paper, we focus on textual data (for a tutorial regarding numerical data, see Bosma & van Witteloostuijn, 2024).

Textual content extraction. Textual content is not only the primary focus of this paper, but also of most current applications of web scraping in organizational research. Extracting such content is sometimes straightforward, and merely a matter of stripping away HTML code. Other times, text is generated by client-side code that may not be captured or that must be executed in order to capture the correct appearance to the user, leading to missing data.

DNS information. Domain Name System (DNS) records are an essential part of the website, as they include the hostname part of the URL and are often part of the brand of the company. Related to the DNS records, the WHO IS information provides valuable data about a company's domain registration. This includes the domain's registration and expiration dates, which can indicate how long a company has been present online. Such information is valuable in assessing a company's digital longevity and maturity, and its adaptation to the online ecosystem over time (Blazquez & Domenech, 2014).

Server headers. Server headers offer a different kind of insight, revealing technical details about a company's web server and infrastructure. Headers typically include response codes, which can indicate the status of a webpage, and content types, which specify the nature of the content being served. These headers can also provide information about the server technology used by the company, offering clues about their commitment to modern digital practices and security measures (Domenech et al., 2012).

Hyperlinks. Examining the hyperlinks within a company's website can uncover its network of associations and affiliations. By analyzing which external domains are linked, insights can be gained about a company's business relationships, partnerships, industry connections, and the like. This form of analysis can be instrumental in understanding a company's market position, its collaborative or competitive dynamics, and its network position (Vaughan et al., 2006).

Website code analysis. The HTML code of a website reflects the company's technical capabilities and approach to web design. Analyzing this code can provide insights into the level of sophistication in the company's web development practices. It can reveal whether a company is using cutting-edge web technologies or outdated methods, providing an indirect measure of its technological advancement and digital maturity (Crosato et al., 2021, 2023).

PDF content and metadata. Companies often use PDFs to publish relevant documents. The text within these documents, along with their metadata, can be a rich source of information. PDF metadata such as the creation date can have a huge potential for retrospective analyses, linking textual content to specific timeframes and enabling an understanding of the company's evolution (Blazquez et al., 2018).

Non-textual content. While currently less common in content extraction, certainly so within organizational research, the analysis of non-textual elements such as images holds future potential. As image recognition and processing technologies advance, they may offer new ways to extract meaningful information from visual content on company websites (Villarroel Ordenes & Zhang, 2019).

To sum up, content extraction from company websites is a complex process that goes beyond just scraping textual content. It involves analyzing a variety of data types, each offering unique insights into a company's operations, history, technological infrastructure, and relationships. This comprehensive approach is crucial for an in-depth and accurate understanding of a company's digital presence, and what that can tell about the company's non-digital existence. As technology continues to evolve, new methods and types of content extraction are likely to emerge, further enriching the field of web-based company analysis. Generally, processing the different content types is a computational matter, in which small choices may have a relatively large impact. Reproducibility of these computational choices is therefore of key importance.

435 From text content to quantitative data

Below, we briefly summarize the steps required to convert the obtained text content into meaningful, reliable, and valid quantitative measures. In general, managing unstructured texts includes three distinct phases: (1) preprocessing the text; (2) developing the natural language model, including the selection of the appropriate NLP algorithm and the corresponding optimal number of parameters; and (3) applying the model to collected texts in order to obtain a measure of the construct of interest to the organizational researcher. Next, we consider each of these steps

separately, as illustrated in the bottom part of Figure 2, with a focus on the attendant challenges and errors. Regarding NLP algorithms, we provide a more in-depth overview in Section 4.

Preprocessing. Some general practices that are usually implemented in the data preprocessing step include lowercase conversion, the removal of non-alphabetic characters and stop words, and stemming/lemmatization (George et al., 2016; Harakawa & Iwahashi, 2021; Singh & Gupta, 2017). Despite these seemingly standard practices, text preprocessing must not be implemented uncritically, but should consider the type of data and the purpose of the analysis. In this regard, Hickman et al. (2022) provide useful guidelines. For example, if the removal of stop words is implemented in a sentiment analysis aimed at revealing customer satisfaction, the researcher should be careful to handle negations (e.g., “never”, “no”, “not”), because they could reverse the polarity of an expression. Reviews such as “The product was good” and “The product was not good” express two opposing opinions. However, implementing the stop words removal without handling negations will return the same string that expresses only the positive polarity (“product good”), losing relevant information on the negative sentiment. From this simple example, it is clear how the seemingly innocuous “preprocessing” can drastically influence the final output obtained from NLP modeling, resulting in a greater or lesser measurement error depending on how it was implemented.

Text representation. Text representation methods convert preprocessed text into numbers for model processing, with two main approaches: bag-of-words and word embeddings (Harris, 1954; Li & Yang, 2018). The bag-of-words method represents, on the one hand, text by counting word frequencies without considering word order, and an extension, TF-IDF, adjusts for word frequency across all texts to improve classification (Valtonen et al. 2024). Word embeddings, on the other hand, represent words as low-dimensional vectors that capture semantic relationships, though they struggle with contextual nuances and sentence aggregation (Eichstaedt et al., 2021). An improvement on word embeddings, contextual embeddings, uses transformers (Vaswani et al., 2023) to update word vectors based on surrounding context, with recent advances such as sentence transformers that account for full sentence meaning, including negation [see Fyffe et al. (2024) for an overview]. Figure 3 illustrates the impact of the choice of representation. Similar to the choice of preprocessing, the choice of representation can have a large impact on measurement error, particularly on the content validity of web-derived measures.

In Section 7, we briefly discuss the application of explainable NLP (XNLP) techniques to evaluate and address the content validity of representations.

[Insert Figure 3 about here]

Modeling. Text represented as numbers can be processed by models using either supervised or unsupervised learning. Supervised learning, which requires labeled data, includes traditional machine learning (ML) methods such as Support Vector Machines, Naïve Bayes, and Random Forests, and deep learning (DL) methods such as deep neural networks, which include transformer-based models such as BERT and GPT. DL methods, often pretrained on large datasets, enable high performance, but may lack interpretability. Unsupervised learning, used to uncover hidden patterns without labeled data, includes clustering methods such as k-means and hierarchical clustering, as well as topic modeling with Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), which identifies latent topics in text corpora. Both approaches are widely used in organizational research for tasks such as text classification and topic discovery (Kobayashi et al., 2018b, 2018a; Valtonen et al., 2024). In addition to supervised and unsupervised techniques, dictionary-based approaches also play an important role in NLP modeling. These methods rely on manually defined dictionaries—such as predefined lists of positive and negative words—to analyze text, rather than on learning from labeled data. Although dictionary-based systems may lack the scalability and adaptability of both traditional ML and DL methods, they offer high interpretability and transparency, making them especially valuable in contexts where understanding the underlying decision process is critical. Further down the line, in the next Section 4, we will offer a somewhat more detailed review of the available NLP algorithms.

In this step, held-out data that were not involved in training the model are commonly used to evaluate the performance. This is therefore one of the only steps in the entire process at

which direct estimates of the errors incurred are routinely given. Even here, however, other issues may occur. For instance, models are well known to struggle to recognize rare classes in the presence of frequent classes (Samuel & Chechik, 2021), leading to “long-tail bias” when researchers try to measure rare attributes. Further, external generalizability of the performance to new website data can be harmed by confounding – a high-profile case being the failure of Google flu trends (Lazer et al., 2014). Again, paying close attention to content validity of the predictions, perhaps using explainable NLP techniques, is essential, and similar to the interpretability recommendation given by Valtonen et al (2024). Finally, even a perfect NLP-based prediction is only as good as the “ground truth” it is predicting. Since this “ground truth” is often based on surveys or other measures known to be error-prone, any measurement issues with the “ground truth” employed in supervised models will likely spill over into model outputs.

4. Modeling choices in NLP for firm characteristics

The text represented as numbers can be processed by a NLP model. As said, these models can be divided into supervised and unsupervised learning (Birjali et al., 2021). While supervised learning entails that the researcher already knows the classes to be investigated in a text corpus, which is already labeled or will need to be labeled, unsupervised learning is implemented when we want to discover hidden patterns in the text corpus, without the need for predefined prior labeling. Starting from supervised learning, this category includes traditional machine learning (ML) approaches and deep learning (DL) methods, which are usually associated with a specific text representation method: the bag-of-words and word embeddings, respectively.

Focusing on traditional ML approaches, they can be grouped into linear approaches, which classify texts using linear (for binary classification) or hyperplane (for multiclass

classification) decision boundaries, probabilistic classifiers, which predict a probability distribution over a set of classes, and decision trees, where data space is decomposed hierarchically using a condition on the attribute value (the presence or absence of one or more words) to classify texts into a finite number of predefined classes (Birjali et al., 2021). There are several traditional ML approaches and many variations that can be used for text classification (a detailed survey is included in Kowsari et al., 2019), but undoubtedly the most popular ones, also used by organizational researchers, are (i) Support Vector Machine (Joachims, 1998), a linear approach that classifies texts by finding the line or hyperplane that provides the best separation among the text in each class, (ii) Naïve Bayes (Rish, 2001), a probabilistic classifier based on the Bayes' theorem that assigns a text to the class that maximizes the posterior probability, and (iii) Random Forest (Breiman, 2001), which combines the output of multiple decision trees to reach a single result. A detailed discussion of these approaches accompanied by a tutorial can be found in Kobayashi et al. (2018a).

On the other hand, DL methods are more advanced approaches with common characteristic that are based on a deep neural network (NN) architecture (Birjali et al., 2021). A NN (White, 1992) is a model inspired by the function of biological neural networks in brains. In its simplest form, this model includes three layers of nodes (or neurons) – i.e., an input layer (whose nodes are words), a hidden layer (whose nodes are nonlinear functions of linear combinations of words plus a bias), and an output layer (one of the predefined classes). Nodes of two successive layers are connected via links. Each link has a corresponding weight, which determines the influence of a node of the previous layer on the node of the subsequent layer. This simple architecture can be extended by adding more hidden layers, which is the main characteristic of deep NNs (Rodrigues et al., 2022). Deep NNs are capable of learning very

complex representations from large amounts of data, thus producing state-of-the-art results in many application domains, including NLP (Zhang et al., 2018).

The most popular methods are based on transformers, in particular the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) model and its variants (e.g., ALBERT and DeBERTa) (Devlin et al., 2019; Lan et al., 2020; He et al., 2021) and Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) models (e.g., GPT-3 and GPT-4) (Brown et al., 2020; Bubeck et al., 2023). These methods are increasingly used among organizational researchers (Fyffe et al., 2024; Kovács, 2024). While BERT models add a classification layer to the base transformer architecture that acts as a classification algorithm, GPT models are generative transformer-based models capable of generating text. This means that these two classes of models can be applied in an integrated manner, with GPT and BERT models that can be used for text generation and text classification tasks, respectively. For example, GPT models could generate adversarial data (i.e., “fake” examples) to improve the precision of BERT models in classifying data. A detailed discussion including a tutorial on how to integrate these models can be found in Fyffe et al. (2024).

Another key difference between traditional ML approaches and DL methods (and the corresponding text representation methods) is the training process. Indeed, while traditional ML approaches often require training from scratch on a customized training set before being implemented, DL methods are usually pretrained on a large generic training set (e.g., large corpora of text such Wikipedia articles and books) and are therefore ready to be used, meaning they can be employed directly out-of-the-box (Abedu et al., 2024). This paradigm shift is linked to the concept of transfer learning, defined as the reuse of knowledge learned from one or more tasks for new tasks (Wang et al., 2023). In pretrained models, the training phase is typically

limited to the fine-tuning phase, in which the pretrained model is further trained on a customized training set to better adapt to the specific task at hand (Devlin et al., 2019). For example, if a company wants to classify customer reviews of a product as positive or negative, it could use the BERT model, which has already been trained on a large generic corpus of text, and then fine-tune it on a training set of customer reviews of that product, which have been labeled as positive or negative.

One of the main advantages of using pretrained models is their performance, as several studies have demonstrated that these models significantly outperform models trained from scratch in several NLP tasks, including text classification and text generation (Hu et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2019; Ribeiro et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020). Although they represent the state-of-the-art in terms of performance, pretrained models present critical issues related to their interpretability (Doshi-Velez & Kim, 2017). The complex NN structure of these models, which are based on deep neural networks trained on huge (and often unknown) text corpora, makes it challenging for humans to understand how they make decisions – let alone if they do so correctly. This is a problem in fields where the model interpretability is crucial, such as economics and social sciences (Wang et al., 2023), including organizational research (see, e.g., Delios et al., 2024).

It is important to note that no single supervised model is universally the best, as its performance depends on the domain being investigated and the dataset used. In NLP modeling, reducing measurement error requires rigorous cross-validation, which allows us to select the supervised model that performs best on the specific dataset while taking into account the inherent limitations of the “ground truth” data used for training and evaluation. Cross-validation involves not only selecting between different model classes, but also optimizing the parameters of a given

model class and choosing the best text representation method (if we are building a model from scratch). The category of unsupervised learning includes several methods designed for specific tasks, all aimed at discovering hidden patterns in the unlabeled text corpus. Clustering and, especially, topic modeling are the most popular unsupervised learning tasks among organizational researchers (Ashton et al., 2020; Kobayashi et al., 2018b; Valtonen et al., 2024). Clustering is the process of organizing documents in groups (or clusters) of similar documents (Kusrini, 2015). Depending on how clustering is implemented, the literature distinguishes between hierarchical and partitional clustering (Ma et al., 2017). On the one hand, hierarchical clustering involves a hierarchical organization of documents, which can be based on a top-down strategy, known as divisive clustering, or a bottom-up strategy, known as agglomerative clustering (Roux, 2018). In divisive clustering, all documents start in a single cluster that is recursively split into sub-clusters; in agglomerative clustering, each document starts in its own cluster, and these are merged into increasingly larger clusters until a desired number of clusters is achieved.

On the other hand, partitional clustering segments documents into a predefined number of clusters by optimizing an objective function, typically based on the distances of the documents to the centers of their assigned clusters (Kobayashi et al., 2018b). In particular, documents within a cluster have very short distances to each other while having the largest distances to the documents in other clusters. The most popular partitional clustering method is the k-means algorithm (Lloyd, 1982), which assigns iteratively each document to one of the predefined cluster centroids based on the similarity between the document and the cluster centroids. Focusing on topic modeling, it can be defined as the task of identifying latent topics within a collection of documents (Zeng & Hua, 2022). For this purpose, topic models are used, the most

popular of which is the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA; Blei et al., 2003). LDA is a probabilistic model that assumes that each document is a mixture of topics, and each topic is a mixture of words. In practice, each topic within a set of documents is represented as a distribution of words, based on the frequency and co-occurrence of words within the same context (Mohr & Bogdanov, 2013). For a detailed discussion of clustering algorithms and topic models in organizational research, we refer to Kobayashi et al. (2018b) and Valtonen et al. (2024).

Beyond supervised and unsupervised methods, dictionary-based techniques are also utilized by organizational researchers due to their simplicity (Schachner et al., 2024). These approaches require the development of domain-specific dictionaries, such as those for innovation, sentiment, or sustainability — an aspect that serves as both a key strength and a notable limitation. While this tailored approach enhances interpretability and transparency, it often requires developing a unique lexicon for each domain under analysis and, in some cases, even distinct dictionaries within the same domain (for example, the terminology used to describe innovation in R&D-intensive industries may differ significantly from that used in traditional manufacturing or service sectors) (Limosani et al., 2025). Since constructing these dictionaries is a delicate task where subjective judgments can significantly influence the final output, it is crucial to involve subject-matter experts in their development to minimize measurement errors.

5. Example use case: the FIRMBACKBONE project

The FIRMBACKBONE project,² funded by the Dutch Platform Digital Infrastructure in the social sciences and humanities (PDI-SSH-2020), aims to develop a comprehensive, longitudinal

² <https://firmbackbone.nl/>.

data infrastructure on the population of Dutch companies for academic research, addressing the current lack of accessible, detailed, and affordable company data. By creating a “backbone” containing company names and numbers, and enhancing this information through data sources such as web scraping and collaborations with strategic data providers, FIRMBACKBONE provides an extensive dataset for research in fields such as economics, management, entrepreneurship, strategy, and economic geography – that is, organizational research, broadly defined. The data is accessible via the (blind) Secure ANalysis Environment (SANE) of the Netherlands digital infrastructure for the social sciences, known as ODISSEI,³ which ensures data protection, data governance, and long-term data sustainability. Researchers are encouraged to enrich the FIRMBACKBONE dataset with their own data, fostering collaboration and deeper economic insights. In this way, FIRMBACKBONE will grow deeper and longer over time. Here, we discuss a proof-of-concept analysis to measure companies’ sustainability orientation using FIRMBACKBONE’s web-scraped data. We illustrate the steps and discuss the consequent errors and limitations incurred at each step, as well as any mitigation measures taken.

1. **From frame to sample.** We defined our population as all private companies registered in the Netherlands with the Dutch Chamber of Commerce (*Kamer van Koophandel*, or KvK). Thanks to our collaboration with them, the complete Dutch corporate register is available, meaning there is no serious sampling error at this stage. At the same time, the register has its limitations. Illegal businesses, for example, around 0.5% of GDP (Statistics Netherlands, 2024), are excluded. For privacy protection purposes, all sole proprietorships are excluded from the standard FIRMBACKBONE dataset. The data is enriched with annual reports and corporate ownership relations (from the KvK), with

³ <https://odissei-data.nl/>.

employment information (from LISA, a provider of establishment-level employment data), and with a selection of registered Dutch top-level domains (SIDN). Currently, FIRMBACKBONE has scraped 1.84 million websites (.nl), which is approximately 41% of all registered Dutch domains that host an active website.⁴

2. **From business sample to website URLs.** To collect the website URLs, we collaborated with the *Stichting Internet Domeinregistratie Nederland* (SIDN), a registry managing the Dutch top-level domain (that is, all websites ending in .nl). Several biases are introduced at this step. First, there are companies without a .nl website and not all registered domains are reported to FIRMBACKBONE due to privacy considerations. Second, around 50% of registered domains expire every year. Third, a small share of the websites still requires HTTP calls (instead of HTTPS). We mitigate these biases by updating our sample, repeatedly scraping the received domains, and requesting the HTTP version if the HTTPS call fails.
3. **From URLs to scraped data.** We developed our own open-source web scraper (<https://github.com/sodascience/websweep>) to prioritize simplicity, modularity, speed, and compliance with web server policies. We can match the websites to companies using the national corporate identifier (KvK number) provided by the company to SIDN or extracted from the scraped data. We restrict our data to only HTML text and crawl a depth of 3 and a maximum of 100 pages per domain. We prioritize pages where the identifier may be present (e.g., about/contact/conditions) and exclude pages containing

⁴ The number of registered domains on September 2 2024 was 6,223,231 according to the SIDN. At the time of writing this section, they have provided us with 1,845,235 domains that are considered company owned, which covers approximately 29.65% of all registered domains and 40.71% of domains with an active website. A frequently updated overview of all registered .nl domains can be found at SIDN Labs: <https://stats.sidnlabs.nl/en/registration.html>.

words that relate to web shops (e.g., product/shop/search). By cleaning the protocol information, queries, and fragments from the URLs, duplicates are avoided. We obey any robots.txt instruction for all websites, and we limit our calls to one call per second per domain.

4. **From scraped objects to content.** FIRMBACKBONE's open-source scraper provides functionality to extract information from the text using custom regular expressions. We extract corporate identifiers that can be matched with other FIRMBACKBONE data, metadata from the headers, and the page text, without HTML tags or JavaScript. To ensure that the text is processed consistently for pages using different encodings, we normalize the text using Normalization Form KD (NFKD).⁵
5. **From text content to quantitative data.** To convert the textual content to quantitative measures, first the language is identified (English or Dutch) using LangDetect (Jauhiainen et al., 2019). Using language-specific tokenizers from NLTK, which consider linguistic complexities such as contractions and compound words, ensures accurate tokenization (Honnibal & Montani, 2017). Moreover, so-called stop words are omitted. Lemmatization reduces words to their base or dictionary form, which addresses issues of inflection and conjugation (Jurafsky & Martin, 2024; Kobayashi et al., 2018b). For future research expanding to new languages, advanced pipelines like Stanza (Qi et al., 2020) or Trankit (Nguyen et al., 2021) could be incorporated to further enhance multilingual preprocessing.
6. **From preprocessing to NLP model.** For illustrative purposes, we focus on a specific attribute of the firm, namely its sustainability activities. We aimed to measure a firm's

⁵ <https://unicode.org/reports/tr15/>.

sustainability orientation, creating a list of sustainability-related keywords derived from the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs) (Lee et al., 2016) and prior studies (Amini et al., 2018; Asif et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2016). Initial terms included “sustainable”, “renewable”, and “eco-friendly”, among others. We expanded this list using WordNet, a lexical database that provides synonyms and semantic relationships (Miller, 1995). This approach enhanced coverage and reduced the risk of missing relevant content due to vocabulary differences (Turney & Pantel, 2010). We additionally evaluated sentiment to determine the emotional tone of the text. We used the Valence Aware Dictionary and Sentiment Reasoner (VADER), a lexicon and rule-based sentiment analysis tool effective for corporate text (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014). Recent works have also adopted transformer-based sentiment methods in business contexts (e.g., FinBERT) to capture nuanced expressions of sustainability, offering an avenue for future improvements (Araci, 2019). Sentiment scores indicated whether sustainability topics were discussed positively (e.g., “We are committed to reducing emissions”) or negatively (e.g., “Facing challenges in sustainability compliance”).

7. **From NLP model to target measure.** We used Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) for topic modeling (Blei et al., 2003) via the Python library `gensim` (Rehurek & Sojka, 2010) to identify the main sustainability themes. To ensure FIRMBACKBONE’s pseudonymization restrictions, Named Entity Recognition (NER) is used to identify entity revealing data (Liu et al., 2015), and Python library `spacy`’s deep learning capabilities (Honnibal & Montani, 2017) eventually filtered out such entities. This also avoids skewing the analysis due to overrepresentation of company names or specific products (Srinivasa-Desikan, 2018). Finally, a balanced measurement of a company’s

engagement with sustainability topics, the sustainability score, is calculated by integrating three key components: the Match Score – i.e., the proportion of sustainability keywords present in the text; the Advanced Match Score, incorporating synonyms and context-based weighting; and the Sentiment Score, reflecting the overall sentiment of sustainability-related content. The final sustainability score was calculated as:

$$\text{sustainability_score} = \text{sentiment_score} (\text{match_score} + 0.5 \text{ advanced_match_score}).$$

By following these steps, the FIRMBACKBONE project shows how to effectively measure firm characteristics using language models, while addressing the challenges of representation, measurement, and computational errors outlined in our framework. Clearly, the associated potential errors model performance, out-of-domain generalization errors, ground truth bias, and construct validity, are context specific and cannot be mitigated by the FIRMBACKBONE approach, but should be accounted for by the researcher.

While NLP has advanced the measurement of firm characteristics through textual analysis, and although we can and should apply a series of error mitigation strategies (as explained above), challenges related to bias, transparency, and validity persist. After all, organizations may strategically use language to influence NLP models, leading to skewed measurements. However, recent developments in Explainable NLP (XNLP) provide tools to enhance content validity by disclosing how specific inputs impact model decisions, thereby identifying potential biases and manipulations in organizational texts. The value added of XNLP is manifold. In this section, we briefly discuss three key examples of how the application of XNLP can help to improve organizational research using NLP.

First, XNLP can **address bias**. Organizations are increasingly aware that their digital texts influence stakeholders' perceptions and can affect metrics such as firm valuation or Company Social Responsibility (CSR) scores. For instance, this awareness may lead firms to deliberately use specific keywords or phrases—such as “sustainable”, “eco-friendly”, or “green initiatives”—to project a favorable image without substantive actions to support these claims. Such practices can result in “greenwashing”, where the company’s communication does not align with its actual environmental performance (Delmas & Burbano, 2011). Traditional NLP models might interpret the frequent use of these terms as indicators of genuine commitment to sustainability, leading to inflated CSR ratings. This manipulation brings up a threat to the validity of measurements derived from textual data, potentially misleading investors, regulators, and other stakeholders relying on these assessments. Recent studies have highlighted the importance of addressing such biases in NLP models. For example, Ong et al. (2024) discussed the challenges of subjectivity and bias in AI models analyzing company sustainability disclosures. They emphasized that sustainability assessments are often prevented by incomplete and ambiguous data, as well as potential bias in analysts’ evaluations. To address these issues, they highlighted the importance of transparency and explainability in AI-driven analyses.

Second, XNLP can **enhance content validity**. XNLP provides methodologies to interpret and understand the inner workings of NLP models. Techniques such as SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) (Lundberg & Lee, 2017) and LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) (Ribeiro et al., 2016) can identify which features most influence a model’s predictions. By analyzing feature importance, researchers can find overreliance on certain keywords that may not accurately reflect the firm’s actual practices. For instance, if an NLP model’s positive CSR assessment heavily depends on the presence of “green” keywords, XNLP

techniques can highlight this dependency. This insight allows researchers to adjust the model or incorporate additional data sources to reduce the bias, increasing the content validity of the measurement. For instance, Ong et al. (2024) applied XNLP techniques to company sustainability reports. By using SHAP values, they uncovered instances where firms overused sustainability-related keywords without corresponding actions, enabling stakeholders to better evaluate the authenticity of sustainability claims.

Third, XNLP can **reduce adversarial manipulation in firm valuation**. Firms may try to manipulate valuation measures in opposed situations by modifying their language to positively impact NLP algorithms. Through the identification of differences between the language used and the firm's real performance measures, XNLP may act as a defense mechanism against such manipulations. For example, in financial reporting, firms might use overly optimistic language to mask poor performance (Huang et al., 2014). Through the use of XNLP, analysts are able to find that subjective language, as compared to objective financial metrics, has a disproportionate impact on the model's valuation. This awareness enables a more critical evaluation of the firm's true financial health. (Lachuer & Jabeur, 2022) showed how explainable models could detect patterns in financial and CSR disclosures, aiding auditors and regulators in identifying companies that might be manipulating their statements through strategic language use.

In all, the above reveals that integrating XNLP into organizational research offers several advantages:

- **Improved Measurement Validity:** Understanding which textual features influence model outcomes allows for adjustments that reduce bias, leading to more accurate measurements of firm characteristics (Rudin, 2019).

- **Enhanced Transparency:** XNLP increases transparency, making it easier to explain model predictions to stakeholders, which is essential in practice fields like finance and company governance (Arrieta et al., 2020), and for inferential progress.
- **Detection of Misrepresentation:** By disclosing reliance on potentially manipulative language, XNLP helps in detecting firms that engage in deceptive reporting practices (Guidotti et al., 2018), and in improving measurement validity.

Hence, in conclusion, to use the benefits of XNLP in measuring firm characteristics, the following practices are recommended:

1. **Adopt model-agnostic explanation tools.** Use tools such as LIME and SHAP to interpret model predictions and identify influential features across different models (Ribeiro et al., 2016; Lundberg & Lee, 2017).
2. **Incorporate multimodal data sources.** Combine textual analysis with numerical data such as financial ratios to create more robust models less susceptible to linguistic manipulation (Kumar & Ravi, 2016).
3. **Engage domain experts.** Collaborate with experts in finance, sustainability, or relevant fields to evaluate the plausibility of influential features identified by XNLP (Doshi-Velez & Kim, 2017).
4. **Implement regular model audits.** Periodically review and update models to account for evolving language patterns and new forms of strategic texts by firms (Jacovi & Goldberg, 2020).

So, XNLP is a powerful tool across multiple domains within organizational research—e.g., in crisis management, sentiment analysis, stakeholder engagement, and cultural and ethical analysis—providing deeper insights into organizations’ behavior and performance across large samples. Table 1 provides a concise overview of studies that use XNLP to rigorously analyze and interpret text gathered from company websites.

[Insert Table 1 about here]

6. Conclusion and discussion

Over the past fifteen years, studies using natural language processing (NLP) and language models in organizational behavior have expanded, driven by the rise of websites as a key tool for companies to showcase themselves and their activities. One of the major features of this data is that it is timely and that it can give objective information about subjective points of view by the organization. Because of this, such widely accessible information on the Internet offers great potential to gather data that can be scraped and analyzed to construct reliable and valid measures of firm’s behavior, characteristics, and performance across large(r) samples of organizations. Doing so, however, comes with a wide array of challenges, which must be handled carefully in order to avoid bias and error.

In this paper, we first gave an overview of existing applications of NLP to web scraping data in organizational research, to subsequently provide a taxonomy of challenges associated with such studies, inspired by the total error framework – systematically discussing the steps required to perform such studies rigorously alongside the potential for errors resulting from these challenges. The contribution of this framework is twofold. First, it can aid the *prevention* of errors, by providing researchers aiming to perform new studies with a checklist of challenges to

address. Second, it can aid the *diagnosis* and potential correction of errors, by pointing out potential sources of errors found in validation and replication studies. Finally, we discussed an example application in terms of our framework. Along the way, we offered a brief review of NLP algorithms.

Our endeavor has highlighted the multiplication of challenges that occur when conducting analyses that encompass the entire process, from retrieving raw company website data to performing statistical analyses using NLP. If this is not done carefully, the result is an accumulation of errors, introducing bias that undermines the reliability and validity of measures, and damages the meaningfulness of findings. However, the good news is that several prior studies, reviewed above, demonstrate that the entire process is technically feasible, and that there is empirical evidence for the overall validity of the approach if conducted with care. There is strong evidence that, while imperfect, the outcomes of NLP are correlated with actual behavior, characteristics, and performance of the organizations as measured from administrative datasets and surveys.

Looking forward, we see several important future points of development, of which we would like to highlight three, to safe space. First, an NLP analysis may be combined with other statistical methodologies. For instance, we foresee a range of applications of widely used research techniques, such as matching, randomized controlled trials, and regression discontinuity. In addition, we see potential for more cooperation between organizational researchers and NLP scholars, to the benefit of both.

Second, for the further development of the field, it is important that data become widely available for academic researchers – datasets must be FAIR.⁶ This is especially crucial given the ever-shifting nature of websites and Internet technology (Milligan, 2016), which creates a fundamental challenge for longitudinal research. However, the considerable costs of scraping and storing workable data for further use may be an impediment, as well as the current lack of an adequate academic incentive structure (Lane et al., 2024). To make company data work for policy and research, due to its market- and privacy-sensitive nature, it must be made available in a secure digital infrastructure (Lane, 2021). The Dutch initiative FIRMBACKBONE, for which the web-scraping part is described in this paper, can be considered as one such initiative for the development of such a data ecosystem; others include the ADRF in the United States (Cunningham et al., 2021) and BERD in Germany (Gehrlein et al., 2022).

Finally, a key question is what additional financial investments are needed to make broad company website data accessible to researchers. This requires coordinated efforts to produce what is essentially a public good. We draw a parallel to a significant development in the early 1990s when pseudonymized administrative datasets on companies became available for empirical research. National statistical agencies and other government bodies, supported by national research foundations, led the initiative. While the data were initially collected for other purposes, creating secure digital infrastructures for analyzing pseudonymized firm data was expensive. Individual researchers could not bear these costs, but it was seen as a critical societal investment. We anticipate a similar path for company website data, but collective action is needed to build these digital infrastructures.

⁶ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.

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Figure 1: Web presence of businesses in OECD countries is large.

Source: OECD, goingdigital.oecd.org/indicator/26.

Figure 2.

Steps towards natural language processing-derived measures from organization websites.

Note: At each step, examples of errors associated with the step are given in one of three categories: representation error, measurement error, and computational error.

Figure 3.

The choice of representation drastically changes the semantic location of website texts.

